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active **c**ommunities & **e**nergy
prosumers for the energy **t**ransition

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP9 – Outreach activities for impact enhancement

D9.2 – ACCEPT dissemination and communication plan and activity report v1

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Deliverable is

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Switzerland

- Azienda Elettrica Di Massagno SA

Suggested Actions

Reviewer 1

The next actions should be implemented for the deliverable to be accepted

The next actions may be implemented for deliverable improvement

Formatting issues

Further suggestions/comments/recommendations

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the overall Dissemination and Communication Strategy for the ACCEPT project during the project lifetime and lays the foundations on how dissemination and communication activities should be carried out, which dissemination materials will be provided and how the activities will be documented and evaluated.

It is important to secure a high visibility of the project, to build project awareness and to promote accountability to justify the value of this innovation action. The creation of a Dissemination and Communication Plan at the early stage of the project, increases its impact and enhances subsequent exploitation opportunities.

This report is delivered in the context of **WP9 - Outreach activities for impact enhancement** and delivers a Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) describing the project's strategy, activities and implementation instruments. It will guide the ACCEPT dissemination and communication activities, as well as supporting materials and the continuous monitoring for assessing the results and impacts of the communication and dissemination activities. This deliverable describes how partners and pilot regions are collaborating for a successful dissemination and communication process. It also explains which communication procedures should be followed when reporting or disseminating an activity.

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Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the document

This report provides a comprehensive Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) describing the strategy, activities and implementation instruments of the ACCEPT project. It aims to introduce the dissemination tools and promotional materials, ways of communication and dissemination of project results to relevant end-users and stakeholders, while also communicating aims and outcomes of the ACCEPT project to the general public. The DCP will design and implement different communication strategies, means and materials to address dissemination (tailored to the needs of the main target groups) and communication (to a wider audience). A continuous monitoring activity will enable to assess the results and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities providing regular feedback to the effectiveness of the strategy.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

This document describes in detail on how to define, continuously update, and manage the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication Strategy as well as the planning of Activities. The present report of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is the first version of a series of connected deliverables and will be updated three times during the project lifetime.

Figure 1: Overview of Deliverables in Task T9.1-Dissemination and communication plan definition

This document represents the first version of the DCP and will describe in detail the tasks that will be undertaken to define, continuously update and manage of the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy and planning of activities. This will also further be highlighted in chapter two and twelve of the document.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The dissemination and communication activities in general have a special status with the relationship to other tasks and work packages, as they are related to (almost) every other project activity. Those activities are part of the horizontal project phase, composing all the horizontal supporting activities namely i) dissemination and communication (WP9), where specifically targeted communication and dissemination strategies/actions (e.g. website, publications, conferences, workshops, etc.) will be designed and conducted by the project partners; ii) exploitation (WP8) where all the necessary activities will be performed to enable commercial and research exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes to maximize the project impact during and after its lifetime and iii) project management (WP1) consisting of all administrative, financial and data management activities as well as the overall quality assurance.

Figure 2: Interdependencies of WPs in ACCEPT (source: HYPERTECH presentation ACCEPT KoM)

There are also some particular connections with this task/deliverable and other tasks and work packages within the project.

- Results and insights drawn from tasks of WP3 and WP8, where the consortium will generate recommendations regarding policy/regulation as well as market structures, will be translated in policy briefs to facilitate efficient communication with policy makers
- The DCP covers only dissemination and communication within ACCEPT, while another related activity, namely the exploitation of the project results, is addressed in task T8.2- Exploitation strategy and IPR management

2. Strategy

2.1. Overall dissemination and communication strategy

This section will present the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy, which precedes a more in-depth description of the communication activities to be implemented in the course of the project. The major focus of the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication plan (DCP) is to ensure that the project activities and outcomes are widely spread among the appropriate audiences, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods, as well as to identify potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes, encouraging their participation on a systematic and regular basis.

Basically, the central questions to be addressed by any dissemination and communication strategy are:

- To whom to communicate? (Audience)
- What to communicate? (Messages)
- How to communicate? (Methods and Time)

At this point, it should also be pointed out that the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication activities are intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project results. The efficient publicity and the wide exposure of the project activities and results to targeted stakeholders and media would facilitate the use of these results beyond the project's lifetime and thus, would increase the project impact.

Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation – it's all about reaching out to various audiences. However, the goals behind those outreach activities are different. The EC published an overview, which helps to distinguish between these related and connected outreach frameworks:

Figure 3: Difference between Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation¹

While the aspects of dissemination and communication will be covered in the DCP, aspects of exploitation will be separately covered in T8.2 and the corresponding Deliverables.

Above, the central questions to be addressed by this dissemination and communication strategy are mentioned. What is missing, however, is the question related in relation to the purpose – the “why?”. Why to communicate, why to disseminate, what is the motivation behind these activities and which goals do we wish to achieve? These goals differ for dissemination and communication actions; the most important ones are illustrated in the following section.

¹ European Commission s.a. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. Why they all matter and what is the difference? Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

2.1.1. Objectives

Prior to every communication or dissemination activity there is a motivation or goal, we would like to achieve with such an activity. Whether important project results will be shown to a large audience at an international event or if a community recruitment activity is posted on social media – the general objective is to make the project's work and achievements visible. Having this general goal in mind, further – more detailed – objectives can be formulated:

- Create public awareness, understanding and interest about the scope, objectives and results of the project
- Address all the stakeholders of the project with specific and valuable knowledge and solutions
- Engage the stakeholders and drive them to adopt and implement the project results

2.1.2. Approach

At the beginning of drafting of a strategy it is important to have a clear picture of the basis and foundation, from which this development will start. A good dissemination and communication strategy is always a process in development, as it is important to constantly monitor, re-evaluate and, if necessary, adapt the strategy and the planned actions.

For a successful implementation of a dissemination and communication strategy the choice of the correct dissemination plan and the means to be used for is essential. Dissemination activities will target the public, academic and industrial areas and the target groups cover a wide variety of sectors from high-level to low-level stakeholders, which shows the need for different approaches within the dissemination plan per target group.

In addition, it is important to choose the right dissemination channels, as the usage of social media and the web can also play an important role, apart from the dissemination of the project, promoting possible future cooperation but even more in providing real feedback over the circulation of project and valuable participants' data bank for future projects. The aforementioned methods & channels will prepare for scaling-up of the project solutions and will allow for getting the market ready for their use.

For the general approach it is important:

- To clearly define contributors and relevant target audiences within ACCEPT
- To choose the right supports & channels

All project partners will contribute to the communication and dissemination activities using their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects. The project consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes and academia, to enable to reach a diversified audience. The communication and dissemination activities and experiences by partners will be carried out on various channels (website, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, electronic/printed newsletter, press release, etc.). Within the first phase of the ACCEPT project a questionnaire (Project Partner Form) was created to identify the communication channels used by the PPs in order to plan dissemination activities accordingly.

A dissemination and communication activity report will be compiled regularly to assess D&C results and identify ad hoc contingency measures if needed.

2.1.3. Communication timeline

The ACCEPT communication strategy timeline is structured in three main phases.

Figure 4: ACCEPT communication strategy

- Phase 1 – Initial awareness phase aims at
 - agreeing upon the communication strategy and future activities
 - creating initial awareness in markets, communities & citizens related with the project’s objectives and scope
- Phase 2 – Targeted awareness market phase aims at
 - Creating “targeted awareness” regarding ACCEPT technologies focusing on key players (e.g. communities) and citizens
 - informing the target market about its technological benefits
- Phase 3 – Strategic phase aims at
 - maximizing target market awareness regarding the ACCEPT solution
 - contributing to ensure the project sustainability and full exploitation

2.1.4. Roles and responsibilities

The European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing (EEE) is the organization leading the dissemination and communication within ACCEPT. EEE will prepare and update the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP) and coordinate activities throughout the project period.

However, all partners will use their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects, to contribute to dissemination and communication activities. The consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes and academia, and it is able to reach a diversified audience.

In addition to the general dissemination and communication approach, special attention will be paid to two focus areas. Firstly, the Living Labs need dedicated dissemination activities and strategies to reach out to the end users and local stakeholders in each pilot region. This pilot-oriented dissemination and communication approach is defined in T3.1 and will be described in the corresponding Deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4). GECO as leading organization of these activities is therefore foreseen as Living Lab coordinator for dedicated dissemination and communication activities, as shown in Table 1.

Secondly, the exchange with other projects – either directly or via networks (e.g. BRIDGE Initiative) – needs special attention throughout the project. HYPERTECH will be the coordinator of related actions to ensure a continuous cooperation with similar projects and important networks. This will be done as part of the activities in WP10 and reported in the corresponding Deliverables (D10.1, D10.2, D10.3, D10.4). This coordinative role is also assigned in the following table.

Team member	Role	Contact
Sebastian Koch	Dissemination and communication coordinator Responsible for all communication and dissemination activities in the project	EEE s.koch@eee-info.net
Philipp Novakovits	Public relations officer Responsible for implementation of dissemination and communication activities and networking with other projects and initiatives	EEE p.novakovits@eee-info.net
Ismini Dimitriadou	Coordinator for technical exchange Responsible for the communication and exchange with the BRIDGE Initiative and similar projects	HYPERTECH i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr
Paul Tobin	Living Lab coordinator Responsible for the dissemination and communication activities in the Living Labs	GECO paul.tobin@geco-global.com

Table 1: Roles and coordination of responsibilities in the ACCEPT dissemination and communication activities

2.2. Target groups and key stakeholders

Key stakeholders of the ACCEPT target audience can be grouped into several categories. Table 2 shows several target groups of the project including several high-level and low-level stakeholders.

Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Energy retailers	Citizens / Building residents	EU institutions (EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs)
Aggregators	Facility managers (e.g. EV charging point operators)	National public authorities (industrial committees, national regulation authorities, ministries and regional councils)
DSOs & TSOs	Commercial Customers	Related EU-funded projects
Distributed Renewable Energy Sources	Residential Customers	Organizations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT
ESCOs	Stakeholders at the pilot sites	European technology platforms and respective clusters
Technology providers	General public	Public bodies & environmental organizations
Scientific community		

Table 2: Key stakeholders identified as target audience of ACCEPT

This is an initial list of key stakeholders defined in the early phase of the project. This list will be continuously updated as the project progresses and will be included in the following versions of the dissemination and communication plan.

The ACCEPT project will result in high value for end users, as the solutions provided will be adapted to their needs based on a co-creation process through continuous interaction between the consortium and end user representatives, to ensure a high level of user acceptance. However, the dissemination activities target audience will also go beyond end-users as the main potential customers of the ACCEPT solutions are also decision makers (site managers, CEO, board of directors, etc.) and the project scale-up will need facilitators. Special attention will be given to the dissemination of the project results on national level and EU level to reach out to those mentioned stakeholder groups.

National level

- National exhibitions related to smart grids, energy storage, energy efficiency, etc.
- Expert conferences and discussions
- Workshops and seminars
- Events in pilot regions

EU level

- European Business Council for Sustainable Energy (e5)
- Union of the Electricity Industry – Eurelectric
- European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (ECEE)
- European Energy Exchange Associations (e.g. Europex)

To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, ACCEPT plans to create two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups will be represented – the user group and the stakeholder ecosystem. In the following sections this approach is described more in detail.

2.2.1. User group

The User Group (UG) will comprise the pool of existing and potential participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities. These stakeholders are critical for successful validation and the generation of reliable, trustworthy conclusions. As a result, ACCEPT will establish the UG at the project onset according to the citizen engagement methodology to ensure not only adequate participation in demonstration activities, but also that participants co-create the ACCEPT solution and evaluate it as independent beta users that will generate feedback and recommendations. This will help the consortium identify weaknesses in the user experience and interfaces and lead to improvements for easier market penetration. This campaign will include both physical and digital engagement means/activities and will strive to maintain a constantly open communication channel with the users.

2.2.2. Stakeholder ecosystem

The second key group includes market stakeholders who can provide an independent viewpoint and enhance the exploitation potential of project outputs by contributing to their design and creation. For this purpose, ACCEPT will establish a “Stakeholder Ecosystem” (SE), populate it and actively involve it in project activities in a consultancy, advisory manner. It will include members that are direct stakeholders in the domains of ACCEPT interest and especially key market verticals, such as demand response, building energy management, flexibility management, retailing, etc. The SE will serve the purpose of an Advisory Board with emphasis on market and exploitation aspects, such as:

- Expand the consortium’s viewpoint beyond the mere interest of its members
- Infuse the project with novel ideas regarding new exploitation opportunities and how to address them
- Ensure alignment of project outcomes with the expectations of the market stakeholders
- Enhance the relevance of project outcomes for further national markets in the EU and beyond

The user groups definition and stakeholder ecosystem will further be concretized within M6-18 of the project and established with the responsible partners. The second version of the ACCEPT dissemination & communication plan and activity report will include precise descriptions of the key groups & stakeholder engagement plan.

2.3. Overview of dissemination and communication activities

Within the ACCEPT project, a variety of communication activities will be carried out, using different dissemination means.

- **Raise awareness and engage citizens**
 Dissemination activities toward citizens are very specific and critical to the project success and include:

 - promotion of awareness about project goals and activities among the pilot actors
 - fostering the active acceptance for pilot activities impacting the participants
 - establishment and maintenance of adequate communication channels with all types of pilot participants.
- **Project web portal and social media presence**
 A very important aspect is to create the project web portal in the first months of the project as well as to establish a representative social media presence in the most popular channels. The project website & social media channels will communicate the objectives, activities and results to the public at large and all partners will have an open attitude and share as much as possible with the public through these channels.
- **Project brochure**
 The project brochure will be a key document, to be distributed by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.
- **Participation in fora & thematic events**
 To raise project awareness, to present the project results and to liaise with potential stakeholders, it is foreseen to participate in events like Concertation Meetings, industry and professional initiatives, thematic working groups and "Info Days". Booths in targeted events in each participating country (i.e. InfoSystem expo, annually in Greece, etc.) shall help the project to engage stakeholders from different industrial domains. Participation in the major events (i.e. ICT, Energy 202x, Smart Grid- Technology and Markets, etc.) will give the chance to present the project to professionals involved in smart grids and to potential buyers. These events attract up to 850,000 visitors every year and open the opportunity to present the projects objectives and mission to European policy-makers, stakeholders and the general public.
- **Liaison with professional communities and networks**
 Technological Platforms, Industrial Associations and Initiatives targeting the advancement in Smart Power Electronics, Local Energy Systems/ Microgrids, DR, smart grids, interoperability, energy markets and standardization, are key dissemination/ exploitation fora to be actively utilized by the ACCEPT consortium. Targeted synergies and interactions will be set up, capitalizing the strong links between the consortium partners and such entities. The project will cooperate with EU-funded projects that also focus on the Smart Grids and Demand Response domains, in order to exchange experiences and create synergies.
- **Contributions to regulations and policy-making activities**
 Within the ACCEPT project the work of regulatory bodies and relevant data protection recommendations will be monitored to shape the requirements for ACCEPT applications and services. Moreover, ACCEPT aims to actively contribute to ongoing work of regulation bodies, policy makers and expert groups e.g. through partner involvement in the relevant expert groups of the Smart Grid Task Force.
 In addition to the above means of dissemination, ACCEPT will also produce and disseminate promotional videos, newsletters, press releases, brochures, posters, slides and leaflets presenting the project concept and achievements.
- **Awareness raising and engagement activities to stimulate key target groups**
 To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, ACCEPT plans to create two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups will be represented.
 There will be the "User Group" (UG) which will comprise the pool of potential participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities and the second key group will include market stakeholders. An appropriate "Stakeholder Ecosystem" needs to be found that can be actively involved in the project activities.

3. Visual identity

The visual identity of the project begins with the logo, is established through online appearances (website, social media) and regularly consolidated in print material, brochures, flyers, etc.

3.1. Logo

The logo was created by EEE, it illustrates the project acronym (“ACCEPT”) as well as the project title – “active communities & energy prosumers for the energy transition”.

Figure 5: ACCEPT project logo

In the report “D9.1 – ACCEPT branding, website and social media channels” the symbolism of the logo, the background and the intended messages are described.

The art style and the colors of the logo are used in every visual representation of the project to facilitate the establishment of the project branding and to ensure the brand recognition.

3.2. Graphic style in project presentations

To ensure quick recognition by partners, stakeholders and target audiences, an overall project design was created based on the project logo.

3.2.1. PowerPoint Presentation

A PowerPoint template was created to have a consistent style for all meetings and presentations, which can be edited by the consortium to their specific needs and contexts.

Figure 6: ACCEPT presentation template slides

3.3. Project Leaflet

To share the ideas and goals of the project with as many stakeholders as possible, the ACCEPT general project leaflet will be created.

The main focus for this trifold-leaflet is to create it in a simple language for all stakeholder groups to understand and not go too much into technical detail and lose their interest.

The leaflet will contain:

- A front page including
 - the project logo
 - the project slogan “a digital toolbox for energy communities”
 - project website & social media channels links
- The inside, containing
 - the list of all participating partners by country
 - a map to present all participating countries as well as the locations of the 4 Living Labs
 - general information about the Living Labs
 - short descriptions of the 4 Living Labs
- The project information page with
 - project timeline & key facts
 - project introduction
- A backside including
 - the logos of all project partners
 - the project’s social media channels and website links
 - contact information of the project coordinator (Antonis Papanikolaou from Hypertech) and the dissemination team (Sebastian Koch from EEE)
 - the EU emblem (see 3.4)
 - a disclaimer

The general project leaflet will be finished in M7 of the project.

Figure 7: ACCEPT general project leaflet

3.4. Acknowledging the EU funding

Any communication activity related to the H2020 ACCEPT project needs to acknowledge the EU funding received, according to the grant agreement signed. This means that the EU emblem needs to be displayed with every communication action as well as the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.”

In practice, it looks like this:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

What’s more, when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

4. Homepage

By the end of M3, the official project website was launched. It serves the purpose to not only inform and engage the public about the project and present a chance to contact the project's reference persons, but also connect the consortium through different forms, a common repository for document sharing and mailing lists.

The official ACCEPT project website can be reached at www.accept-project.eu

4.1. Website Content

4.1.1. Project news

Current activities in the project and other project-relevant news

4.1.2. Events

Project events and other project-relevant international events

4.1.3. About the project

Project introduction and description of the work packages

4.1.4. Consortium

Project partner logos with respective subpages with information about the PPs, which was obtained in advance from the PPs via an online form:

- PP Logo
- PP Description
- PP's Role in the project
- Website and social media links
- Location

4.1.5. Living labs

Description of the living labs and location of the pilot sites

4.1.6. Library

Public Dissemination material and media

4.1.7. Legal Notice

4.1.8. Privacy Policy

4.1.9. Footer

- Social media links
- Newsletter registration form
- Twitter feed
- Contact information
- EU emblem and project disclaimer
- Bridge link

Figure 8: ACCEPT website structure

Figure 9: ACCEPT website screenshots

5. Social media

The social media channels will be the backbone of the dissemination and communication activities. Short pieces of information, easy to digest for the reader, presented with illustrations or graphical elements will be issued in a continuous way. Through this, the key messages of the project can be shared with the target audiences. Revision and repetition are in this sense crucial, since the project itself is quite technical and complex topics are addressed.

What's more, social media channels open up the possibility of a dialogue with certain target audiences, networking and exchange with professional initiatives, experts, platforms and organizations. To this end, these channels will be an important platform for establishing exploitation options and cooperation in the later stages of the project.

In M1 of the project, the following social media channels have been established:

Twitter – AcceptH2020
<https://twitter.com/AcceptH2020>

LinkedIn – Accept_H2020
www.linkedin.com/company/Accept-H2020

YouTube – Accept_H2020
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsFhR-shQ8e_nkhqo5D4vVA

Figure 10: ACCEPT Twitter profile

Figure 11: ACCEPT LinkedIn business profile

Figure 12: ACCEPT Youtube channel

5.1. Social Media activity plan

In order to avoid having a one-sided communication and to provide a holistic view of the project and project partners activities, each partner is asked to provide input for our social media channels. This ensures a constant social media activity and a reporting of all aspects of the ACCEPT project.

For every week, there are two project partners chosen to provide some sort of input for our social media channels. Input to our social media isn't limited to concrete project activities, but also various other input, for example:

- A link to a relevant (online) article / news item
- A posting of some related activity within the organization (related publications, participation at some event, results from other related projects, etc.)
- A link to a video related to the project or your current activities

These scheduled social media activities are the foundation of our online communication.

Social Media Activity Plan

February - May 2021

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

Figure 13: ACCEPT Social Media activity plan M2-M5

6. Newsletter

In addition to other communication channels a bi-annual issue of electronic newsletters will help to further educate the project’s target groups, stakeholders and end-users on a regular basis. Other than in social media for example, newsletters leave space to address certain aspects and milestones of the project more in detail.

EEE as dissemination and communication leader will prepare the structure and basic content of the newsletter issues, all partners will contribute if required to highlight certain aspects of their work, reports, intermediate results or pilot site experiences. Content-wise the newsletters be oriented towards the communication-timeline outlined in 2.1.3. In the initial phase of the project awareness raising and information provision will be a central part of the messages to be delivered through this channel. As the project progresses hands-on experiences from the pilot sites as well as technical developments and other project results will come more into focus.

Events and other communication channels (e.g. social media, homepage) will be used to gain subscribers, but also all project partners commit to reach out to their already established networks (on national/regional or international level) to get subscribers for electronic newsletters.

The newsletters will be created using a web-based email marketing service. The distribution will be carried out through a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the project’s website.

Figure 14: sign-up form for newsletters on the ACCEPT website

7. Scientific publications

Dissemination activities concentrate on the diffusion of scientific and technological knowledge, generated within the context of the project, to large groups of relevant stakeholders, both academic and market actors. The aim is to ensure the long-term impact of ACCEPT, in terms of communicating, but also exploiting, the project's results.

To that extent, the dissemination objectives extend beyond activities related to the technical work in ACCEPT, towards reaching out to larger audiences that are active in the relevant fields of research and innovation.

As mentioned in the ACCEPT Description of Work (DoW), this dissemination goal will be achieved primarily by means of publishing scientific articles in journals and organizing/participating in conferences, panels, workshops, roundtables relevant to the project's research and innovation activities. In this way, we will be able to reinforce the project image and brand, cross-fertilize ACCEPT concepts and solutions with state-of-the-art techniques, foster cross-project cooperation and provide a fundamental verification of soundness of project results via peer review.

The action plan to be adopted consists of three distinct steps that are to be repeated in a 6-monthly (in the case of conferences/other events) or yearly basis (in the case of journals):

1. Identification of relevant scientific journals and/or events by the relevant project partners (project coordinator, project dissemination manager, research organizations)
2. Round table between partners for generating a time plan with articles to be published/events to be attended or organized.
3. Implementation of the time plan by the consortium.

In the following tables, we report the results from the first activity listed above, namely the lists of candidate journals and events that can be considered for the project's dissemination purposes. Furthermore, we include a list of open access repositories. The discussion between partners, in order to come up with the detailed time plan of activities, will take place in the upcoming months.

7.1. Relevant Scientific Journals

7.1.1. Classic Scientific Journals

- **IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid**
<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-smart-grid>
 The journal publishes original research on theories and principles of smart grid technologies and systems, used in demand response, Advance Metering Infrastructure, cyber-physical systems, multi-energy systems, transactive energy, data analytics, and EV integration.
- **IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy**
<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-sustainable-energy>
 The journal publishes original research on design, implementation, grid-integration and control of sustainable energy technologies and systems.
- **Elsevier – Applied Energy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy>
 It provides a forum for information on innovation, research, development and demonstration in the areas of energy conversion and conservation, the optimal use of energy resources, analysis and optimization of energy processes, mitigation of environmental pollutants, and sustainable energy systems.
- **Elsevier – Journal of Cleaner Production**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-cleaner-production>
 An international, transdisciplinary journal focusing on Cleaner Production, Environmental, and Sustainability research and practice. Subject areas include, but are not limited to: Cleaner production and technical processes, Sustainable Development and Sustainability, Sustainable Consumption, Environmental and sustainability assessment, Sustainable Products and Services, Corporate sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility, Education for Sustainable Development, Governance, legislation, and policy for sustainability

- **Elsevier – Energy and Buildings**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-and-buildings>
 An international journal publishing articles with explicit links to energy use in buildings.
- **Elsevier - Energy Research & Social Science**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-research-and-social-science/>
 Publishes research examining the relationship between energy systems and society.
- **Elsevier - Energy Policy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-policy>
 International peer-reviewed journal addressing the policy implications of energy supply and use from their economic, social, planning and environmental aspects.
- **MDPI – Energies**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies>
 Energies is a peer-reviewed, open access journal of related scientific research, technology development, engineering, and the studies in policy and management and is published semimonthly online by MDPI. The journal covers research in energy engineering and sciences, with a strong focus on energy storage and conservation, biomass and bioenergy, renewable energy, electricity supply and demand, energy in buildings, and on economic and policy issues. The journal also welcomes papers on related topics such as energy modelling and prediction, integrated energy systems, energy planning and management, provided such topics are within the context of the broader multi-disciplinary scope of energy.
- **MDPI – Electricity**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/electricity>
 Electricity is an international peer-reviewed open access journal on electrical engineering published quarterly online by MDPI. The scope of Electricity includes: Electric Power Systems, Energy Conversion, Power Markets and Economics, Smart Grids and Smart Electricity Applications, Electricity Storage, Electric Transportation, Electric Infrastructure and Applications, Environmental Issues and Electric Engineering Education.
- **SAGE - Energy and Environment**
<https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/energy-environment/journal202462#ManuscriptPrep>
 Interdisciplinary journal that encourages dialogue between the social sciences as energy demand and supply are observed and analyzed with reference to politics of policy-making and its implementation.
- **Wiley - International Journal of Energy Research**
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1099114x>
 Focus on energy management, production, conversion, conservation, systems, technologies and applications, and their impact on the environment and sustainable development.
- **Springer - Energy, Sustainability and Society**
<https://energysustainsoc.biomedcentral.com>
 Forum for research, development & implementation of sustainable energy systems.

7.1.2. Hybrid Scientific Journals (research, but also for professional communities)

- **Elsevier - Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/renewable-and-sustainable-energy-reviews>
 Focuses on renewable and sustainable energy in order to bring together the research community, the private sector and policy and decision makers.
- **Science Direct - Renewable Energy**
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-energy>
 Renewable Energy seeks to promote and disseminate knowledge on the various topics and technologies of renewable energy systems and components. The journal aims to serve researchers, engineers, economists, manufacturers, NGOs, associations and societies to help them keep abreast of new developments in their specialist fields and to apply alternative energy solutions to current practices.

7.2. Relevant Scientific Conferences and Workshops

7.2.1. Conferences

- **Energy and Climate Transformations: 3rd International Conference on Energy Research & Social Science**
 Manchester, UK, 4-7 April 2022
<https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/international-conference-on-energy-research-and-social-science>
 The conference is the premier global forum for exploring the nexus of energy and society.
- **BEHAVE European Conference on Behaviour and Energy Efficiency**
 Copenhagen, Denmark, April 2022
<https://c2e2.unepdtu.org/events/behave-2020-6th-european-conference-on-behaviour-and-energy-efficiency/>
 The targeted audience will include scholars, energy efficiency policymakers and regulators, decision-makers, international development workers, as well as practitioners and the private sector.
- **Energy, Society and Sustainability**
 Zurich, Switzerland 14–15 January 2022
<https://waset.org/energy-society-and-sustainability-conference-in-january-2022-in-zurich>
 A premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Energy, Society and Sustainability.
- **World Sustainable Energy Days**
 Wels, Austria, June 2022
<https://www.wsed.at/en/programme/european-energy-efficiency-conference.html>
 Conference with mix of academic and industry presentations on energy efficiency and sustainable energy target; audience includes households, businesses and municipalities.
- **RGS-IBG Annual International Conference**
 Newcastle University, UK, 30 August - 2 September 2022
<https://www.rgs.org/research/annual-international-conference/>
 The three-day RGS-IBG Annual International Conference attracts over 2000 geographers from around the world.
- **EEEIC 2022, '23, '24 (annual event)**
 Place and Date TBA
<https://www.eeeic.net/eeeic/> (URL of recent event)
 International Conference on Environmental and Electrical Engineering

- **ENERGYCON 2022 (Bi-annual event)**
 Riga, Latvia
<https://www.showsbee.com/fairs/IEEE-EnergyCon.html>
 Covers a broad range of electric power and energy systems topics.
- **UPEC 2022, '23, '24 (Annual event)**
 Place and Date TBA
<https://upec2021.tees.ac.uk/> (URL of recent event)
 International Universities Power Engineering Conference
- **IEEE ISGT Europe 2022, '23, '24 (Annual event)**
 Place and Date TBA
<https://ieee-isgt-europe.org/> (URL of recent event)
 The IEEE PES ISGT Europe conference is one of the two IEEE PES flagship conferences organized in Europe and has established a strong reputation in the last years. It focuses on industrial and manufacturing theory and applications for the wide use of information and communication technologies and integrated renewable and distributed energy resources on the electric grid
- **PowerTech 2023 (Bi-annual event)**
 Place and Date TBA
<https://www.powertech2021.com/> (URL of recent event)
 PowerTech is the anchor conference of the IEEE Power & Energy Society (PES) in Europe and provides a forum for researchers and engineers involved in electric power and energy engineering to share ideas and results.
- **Enlit Europe (Annual event)**
 Milan, Italy, 30 November – 2 December 2021
<https://www.enlit-europe.com/live>
 Enlit is a constantly growing, inclusive and end-to-end forum that addresses every aspect of the energy agenda.

7.2.2. Workshops

- **Energy Geographies Research Group (EnGRG)**
<https://www.energygeographies.org>
 A research group within the RGS with meetings, webinar and events hosted throughout the year, most notably at the RGS-IBG Annual International Conference.

7.3. Open Access Repositories

- <https://arxiv.org/>
arXiv is an open-access repository of electronic preprints and postprints approved for posting after moderation, but not peer review. It consists of scientific papers in the fields of mathematics, physics, astronomy, electrical engineering, computer science, quantitative biology, statistics, mathematical finance and economics, which can be accessed online.
- <https://datadryad.org/stash>
Dryad is an international open-access repository of research data, especially data underlying scientific and medical publications. Dryad is a curated general-purpose repository that makes data discoverable, freely reusable, and citable.
- <https://figshare.com/>
Figshare is an online open access repository where researchers can preserve and share their research outputs, including figures, datasets, images, and videos. It is free to upload content and free to access, in adherence to the principle of open data.
- <https://zenodo.org/>
Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN.[1][2] It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts.
- <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
Fast publication and open peer review for research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding across all subject areas.

8. Media

There are various communication channels, which can be subsumed in this category. These channels can differ very much in their character regarding aspects like range, however, one aspect remains the same with respect to the project’s approach to the utilization of them: media channels will be utilized throughout the project in an “ad hoc”-way.

Dissemination in magazines, blogs, TV or even through print media via press releases won’t be strictly scheduled, but utilized in an on-demand way. Taking developments, milestones and especially deployment actions in the pilot sites into account, appropriate media channels will be chosen for specific dissemination actions. Having said that, even within the broad range of media-related communication channels some activities will be carried out on a more regular basis, other actions (like TV contributions) will be primarily based on current developments in the project, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 15: regularity of dissemination activities in media channels

9. Events & Networking

9.1. External events

An effective means for the dissemination of project findings, learnings and key outputs are external events (national and international), such as conferences, fora, panel discussions, summits, symposiums etc. Members of the ACCEPT project should look for and inform the consortium of suitable external events where the project can be represented to increase its visibility. They should also explore opportunities for actively participating in such events to raise awareness on the project and connect with possible key industry stakeholders.

An indicative list of relevant external events to be targeted in 2021 can be found in Table . The below list of external events will be updated by Project members as the project progresses.

Event Name	Date(s)	Location	Link	Priority
CIRE2021	20-23 September 2021	Digital event	https://www.cired2021.org/	Low
Sustainable Places 2021	29 September – October 2021	Rome, Italy	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/	High
EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) 2021	25-29 October 2021	Digital event	https://eusew.eu/	High
Enlit Europe	30 November – 2 December 2021	Milan, Italy	https://www.enlit-europe.com/	High

Table 3: Indicative list of upcoming external events in 2021

The BRIDGE General Assembly, held annually, is also a high priority event for the dissemination of all ACCEPT outputs and will be targeted in early 2022.

The goal is to participate to at least 30 external events within the project lifetime. This goal should be revisited throughout the project and adjusted, if necessary, especially in cases where participation to external events is hindered by externalities, such as the persistent pandemic crisis.

Before participating in an external event:

If a partner wishes to participate in an external event representing the ACCEPT project, they should let the Project Coordinator and the Dissemination and communication coordinator know in advance, providing them with key information on the event, such as:

- the type and title of the event,
- the event dates,
- the level and nature of participation of the partner at the event (e.g. presentation, panel discussion),
- the event program (if available),
- an estimation of the event attendance costs, etc.

This will allow, on the one hand, to keep track of all project-related dissemination activities and optimally manage the dissemination resources of the project, and on the other hand, to provide the relevant partner with guidance and project dissemination material (if required and where available).

After participating in an external event:

After participating in an external event, and within the first month following the event, relevant partners should update the Dissemination and communication coordinator on the key outcomes/outputs from their participation at the event. Any dissemination material (such as fliers, presentations, etc.) prepared and shared with external stakeholders during the external event, as well as any available event proceedings, should be included in the communication to the Dissemination and communication coordinator. The Dissemination and communication coordinator should then update accordingly the wider consortium and upload all event-related material on the project repository in a folder indicating the event name and dates.

It is strongly recommended that, every time partners actively participate in external events, a specific communication piece is prepared and shared with the wider ACCEPT consortium, as well as publicly via social media (including on the project’s own social media pages) and the websites of the project and ACCEPT partners.

Finally, a list of all past external events attended should be maintained and regularly updated by the Dissemination and communication coordinator. This list will be included in the different iterations of the “ACCEPT dissemination and communication plan and activity report”.

9.1.1. Past external events

The table below provides a list of past external events, for M1 to M6 of the project, in which ACCEPT partners took part representing the consortium.

Event Name	Date(s)	Location	Partner(s)	Contributions	Link
BRIDGE GA 2021	2-4 March 2021	Digital event	HYPERTECH, RINA-C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the ACCEPT project during the first plenary session of the GA • Business modelling from a different perspective by the ACCEPT project – as part of parallel session 6 of the Business Models Working Group 	BRIDGE GA 2021

Table 4: List of past external events where ACCEPT was represented (M1-M6)

10. Synergies with other EU projects

Synergies with other EU projects are part of WP 10, since it is also part of the dissemination & communication of the project, a brief outlook on the activities follows:

One of the main pathways for disseminating the key outcomes and learning points of ACCEPT, as well as gaining useful insights into what other EU projects are currently doing in the space of energy communities, demand flexibility and consumer-centric energy services to assist with the energy transition, is the establishment of strategic synergies with similar EU projects, as well as participating in the BRIDGE initiative.

With regards to the establishment of key synergies with other projects, ACCEPT is currently part of a 'focus group' with the projects HESTIA, SENDER, REDREAM and i-FLEX, all funded under the same H2020 call. The 'focus group' has agreed to discuss common challenges, exchange experiences, lessons learned and best practices under specific thematic meetings organized on an ad-hoc, yet regular, basis. The first thematic meeting was held in May 2021 and focused on user engagement and how EU projects are tackling challenges associated with it. The 'focus group' has also agreed to create a common repository where useful open-access material can be exchanged among projects.

Finally, the ACCEPT project is part of the BRIDGE initiative, with representatives in the Data Management, Business Models, Consumer and Citizen Engagement and Regulation Working Groups. Moreover, the ACCEPT project has recently agreed to actively participate in Action 3 of the Data Management WG, looking at the interoperability of flexibility assets, and co-chair the Business Models Working Group.

Details on the synergies between the ACCEPT project and other similar projects, as well as on the contributions of the ACCEPT project to the BRIDGE initiative, are reported as part of the WP10 deliverables (public deliverables).

Updates on the activities & synergies with other EU projects will be upcoming version versions of the ACCEPT dissemination & communication plan and activity report.

11. Outreach on pilot site level

11.1. Living Lab Branding

For the best possible stakeholder engagement within the 4 Pilot Sites of the project, the consortium decided to create an individual branding for each Living Lab, based on the LL Partner's corporate Identity in national language. The main task was to create communication material in the partners design while still have the visual & contextual connection to the ACCEPT project. The focus was on the value propositions of the different services tested in each demo from the customer's perspective.

- **Aspra Spitia:** Greece/ Greek
- **Culemborg:** Netherlands/ Dutch
- **Murcia:** Spain/Spanish
- **Massagno:** Switzerland/Italian

Figure 16: Living Lab Leaflet Aspra Spitia / Greece

Figure 17: Living Lab Leaflet Culemborg / Netherlands

Figure 18: Living Lab Leaflet Murcia / Spain

Figure 19: Living Lab Leaflet Massagno / Switzerland

11.2. Pilot Site Activity

As this version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is provided at the beginning of the project and the pilot sites are still at the beginning of their pilot activities, the report about communication and dissemination actions carried out at the pilots will be provided at a later stage. Version 2 of the dissemination and communication plan and activity report will include updates of the pilot partners, regarding their activities on pilot site level. In addition, tasks 3.1 & 3.4 will be used to give a summary of the activities that were carried out.

12. Monitoring & Evaluation

12.1. Activity schedule

The following table gives a detailed overview of the planned dissemination and communication activities within the ACCEPT project. This plan will be the guideline and basis for evaluation for all dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime.

Activity	Schedule	Responsibility
Project website	M1-M3: Design and Development of the project's website	EEE
	M4-M42: Regular update of the website content	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Social media	M1-M2: Setup of social media channels	EEE
	M2-M42: Constant social media activity according to social media activity plan	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Scientific publications	M6-M42	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Workshops	M6-M42	All Partners
Electronic newsletters	M6-M42 Bi-Annual Issue	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Press releases	M1-M42	All Partners
Dissemination material	M7: General project Leaflet created	EEE
	M6: Leaflets for stakeholder engagements within the Living Labs created	EEE Contribution: all Partners
	M6-M10 Project Rollup & Poster	EEE
Participation in external events	M1-M42	EEE & Hypertech Contribution: all Partners
Project presentation	M1-M3	EEE
Project video / slideshow	M6-M32 1 initial version + update	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Trainings / webinars	M12-M42	All Partners
Presentation & feedback session	M6-M42	All Partners

12.2. Monitoring of dissemination and communication activities

The dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime will be regularly monitored in order to enable and adequate evaluation of the communication performance of the consortium. The monitoring of the performed dissemination and communication activities carried out by the ACCEPT project partners is not only important as the progress can be documented, but also to initiate countermeasures in case of not fulfillment of the planned target values. Those target values, as basis for the evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities, are represented by special KPIs that indicate a qualitative and quantitative evaluation. The progress of activities and the fulfillment of the different KPIs will be reported in each of the updated versions of the DCP.

Figure 20: Dissemination & Communication Monitoring tool

12.3. Performance & KPIs

The following table shows the summary chart of ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication activities measured with respective KPIs.

Communication & Dissemination Supports and Channels	KPIs	Main Target Stakeholders		
		Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Project Documentation				
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates	X	O	X
Project Publications				
Project newsletter	7 (bi-annual issues) 100 Subscribers	X	X	X
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (on average)	X	O	X
Project Leaflet	1 initial version + updates 500 copies printed	X	X	O
Poster	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Rollup	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	X	O	X
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	X	O	X
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	X	X	X
Pilot Site Leaflets	4 different versions	O	X	O
Online Presence				
Project website	1 website, monthly updated 5.000 visitors	X	X	X
Related websites	10+	Depending on specific website		
LinkedIn	At least 1 weekly update 150 Follower	X	X	X
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update 500 Follower	X	X	X
Youtube	50 Follower	X	X	X
Events				
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	X	X	X
Training sessions	3	X	X	X
External events	30+	Depending on specific event		

Caption:

X Main target

O Secondary target